

Location of the S-c gene on chromosome 3. Markers are on the right and map distances (in cM) are on the left.

F₂ Segregation Patterns for RFLP markers in the cross between E₁ and E₅.

Locus	j/j	j/i	i/i	χ^2 (1:2:1)
RG227	0	51	53	50.1
RG166	2	52	50	44.3
RG369	2	52	50	44.3

Distorted F₂ ratios were observed for the three RFLP markers in the cross (see table). The results suggest the use of the one-locus sporo-gametophytic model in explaining F₁ pollen sterility in cultivated rice (Zhang and Lu 1993).

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Chloroplast ribosomal protein genes encoded in rice nuclear genome

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Plant cells contain three distinct types of ribosomes that are found in the cytosol, mitochondria, and chloroplasts. Chloroplast ribosomes are structurally and

functionally very similar to eubacterial ribosomes, most likely reflecting their endosymbiotic origin. Several chloroplast ribosomal protein genes have been cloned and sequenced, mostly in dicotyledonous plants. Publication of complete nucleotide sequences of the rice chloroplast genome (Hiratsuka et al 1989) has allowed scientists to predict about two-thirds of the 55-60 chloroplast ribosomal proteins encoded in the nucleus. These nucleus-encoded chloroplast ribosomal proteins are synthesized on cytoplasmic 80S ribosomes as precursor polypeptides with a transit peptide sequence, which is cleaved off during transport into the organelle.

We isolated and sequence cDNA clones for nuclear-encoded genes *rpl13* and *rpl28*, which encode chloroplast ribosomal proteins L13 and L28, respectively, in rice. With poly(A)⁺-RNA isolated from green leaves of 10-d-old rice seedlings (*Oryza sativa* L. cv Nipponbare), cDNA libraries were constructed in λ ZAPII (Stratagene). Based on the highly conserved region among chloroplast ribosomal protein sequences reported in other plants, such as tobacco and spinach, the corresponding rice DNA fragments were amplified using reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction and used as probes. Nucleotide sequences of positive clones were determined using the dideoxy nucleotide chain termination method on double-stranded DNA templates.

The cDNA clone of *rpl13* consists of 1,076 nucleotides, including poly(A)₂₉ tail, and contains an open reading frame of 702 bp. The cDNA clone of *rpl28* consists of 781 nucleotides, including poly(A)₂₀ tail, and contains an open reading frame of 411 bp. Compared with sequences from spinach and tobacco, amino acid sequences deduced from cDNA sequences of *rpl13* and *rpl28* are more conserved in the mature peptide region, which is actually assembled into chloroplast ribosome. than in the transit peptide region. The mature L13 protein has 85 and 58% amino acid sequence identity with the counterparts of spinach (Phua et al 1989) and *Escherichia coli* (Isono et al 1985), respectively, in the homologous overlapping regions (see figure, region C). The amino acid identity of the mature

A schematic representation of local alignment of amino acid sequences of rp128. Predicted amino acid sequence of rice rp128 cDNA was aligned with the homologues of spinach and E. coli using MACAW algorithm (Lawrence et al 1993). Darker shade indicates sequence blocks with higher homology scores.

protein of L28 is 75 or 32% relative to tobacco (Yokoi and Sugiura 1992) and *E. coli* (Lee et al 1981). The mature L13 protein of rice contains 24 amino acid residues of N-terminal extension (see figure, region B), which is 16 residues shorter than that of spinach.

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